

The Wheatstone Bridge Flow Network: Illustrative Example for Maximum Entropy Analysis

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Abstract

This study applies the maximum entropy (MaxEnt) method to the prediction of (probabilistic) flow rates and potential differences on a Wheatstone bridge, as a simple example of a potential-driven flow network. Using a multivariate Gaussian prior, the MaxEnt formulation is analytic, even for nonlinear resistance functions. The analytical form of the partition function enables factorisation and rapid solution, without requiring numerical solution of integrals. Several problem specifications are analysed both algebraically and numerically, including for (a) linear resistance functions, (b) non-linear (quadratic) resistance functions, (c) an unknown resistance and (d) uncertain resistances, to demonstrate nonlinear applications of the MaxEnt method.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of a “flow network” – a set of nodes connected by flow paths – can be applied in many different disciplines, in particular to the water distribution, sewerage, electrical and transport networks of human civilisation. Traditionally, such networks are analysed deterministically by simultaneous solution of their physical laws (Kirchhoff laws) in conjunction with sufficient parameter values to provide a closed-form solution. The use of probabilistic inference, based on the maximum entropy (MaxEnt) method, has been applied for many years to transport networks [1, 2], but only to a limited extent to water distribution and electrical networks [3, 4, 5]. In physics, there has been considerable interest in the statistical mechanics of communications and human social networks [6, 7, 8].

In this study, we apply the maximum entropy (MaxEnt) method to the prediction of (probabilistic) flow rates and potential differences on an potential-driven flow network with the topology of a Wheatstone bridge [9, 10]. Using a multivariate Gaussian prior, the MaxEnt formulation is shown to be analytic, even for nonlinear resistance functions. The analytical form of the partition function enables factorisation and rapid solution, without requiring the numerical solution of integrals reported in previous studies [3, 4]. Several problem specifications are examined both algebraically and numerically, to provide a learning tool for the application of MaxEnt to flow networks and other problems with nonlinear constraints.

2. ANALYSES

2.1 Prediction of Flow Rates and Potentials

Consider a Wheatstone bridge flow network as illustrated in Figure 1, with 4 nodes, 5 internal edges and 2 external links. This structure can represent any potential-driven network, such as a pipe flow network, electrical network or chemical reaction network. Since the flows can reverse, Figure 1 represents an undirected graph structure. Using a simplified notation [3, 4, 5], there are 5 internal flow rates $\mathbf{Q} = [Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4, Q_5]^T$, 2 external flow rates $\Theta = [\Theta_A, \Theta_D]^T$ and 5 internal potential differences $\Delta H = [\Delta H_1, \Delta H_2, \Delta H_3, \Delta H_4, \Delta H_5]^T$. We also consider the potential difference across the network ΔH_{AD} . For convenience, we adopt a sign convention for positive flow rates $Q_i > 0$ and negative potential differences $\Delta H_i < 0$, shown by the blue arrows in Figure 1. For flows or potential differences in the opposite directions, $Q_i < 0$ and $\Delta H_i > 0$.

Figure 1: An undirected Wheatstone bridge flow network with potential-driven flows (blue arrows show the sign convention for positive flow rates and negative head differences).

In traditional network analysis, all flow rates and potential differences are considered to be deterministic (equal to the steady-state value), connected by resistance functions of the form $\Delta H_i = -R_i(Q_i)$ for each edge i . In contrast, in MaxEnt analysis, each quantity is considered to be probabilistic, even at the steady state. The constraints are then applied to expected values of each quantity $\langle \cdot \rangle$, interpreted either as time or ensemble averages. The resistance functions are also applied in the form $\langle \Delta H_i \rangle = -R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)$. The MaxEnt formulation provides a probabilistic solution when the problem is underconstrained, which reduces to the deterministic solution when the problem is fully constrained.

The first step in MaxEnt analysis is to define a probability measure over the uncertainties in the problem [5]. For the flow network in Figure 1, the resistance functions allow a dramatic reduction in the number of independent variables, enabling the problem to be specified in terms of \mathbf{Q} and Θ . The uncertainties can then be represented by the joint probability density function (pdf) $p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)$, giving the relative entropy function [3]:

$$\mathfrak{H}_\Omega = - \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)} d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta = - \left\langle \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)} \right\rangle \quad (1)$$

where $q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta)$ is the prior pdf and $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^7$ is the combined domain. The prior specifies the user's *a priori* belief of the distribution of flow rates in the absence of constraints, and is essential for continuous variables to ensure scale invariance [13].

The constraints on the entropy function due to the Wheatstone bridge, written in expectation form, include [3]:

(I) The normalisation constraint, expressing the conservation of probability:

$$1 = \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta = \langle 1 \rangle \quad (2)$$

(II) Kirchhoff's first law for the conservation of mean flow rates at each node A to D, respectively:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} (\Theta_A - Q_1 - Q_3) p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta \\ \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} (Q_1 - Q_2 - Q_5) p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta \\ \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} (Q_3 + Q_5 - Q_4) p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta \\ \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} (Q_2 + Q_4 - \Theta_D) p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \Theta_A - Q_1 - Q_3 \rangle \\ \langle Q_1 - Q_2 - Q_5 \rangle \\ \langle Q_3 + Q_5 - Q_4 \rangle \\ \langle Q_2 + Q_4 - \Theta_D \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle \quad (3)$$

(III) Kirchhoff's second law for a vanishing mean potential difference around each enclosed loop ABC and BDC, respectively:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle) + R_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle) - R_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle) \\ R_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle) - R_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle) - R_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{g}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle) \quad (4)$$

The flow network may also be subject to some of the following constraints:

(I) A mean inflow or outflow constraint, for example:

$$\langle \Theta_A \rangle = \int \cdots \int_{\Omega} \Theta_A p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta = \overline{\Theta_A} \quad (5)$$

(II) An internal mean flow rate constraint, such as on $Q_i \in \mathcal{Q}$:

$$\langle Q_i \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \cdots \int Q_i p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta = \overline{Q_i} \quad (6)$$

(III) A mean head difference constraint between a pair of nodes, represented by a ‘‘pseudo-loop’’ in the Hardy-Cross method, for example:

$$-\langle \Delta H_{AD} \rangle = R_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle) + R_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle) = -\overline{\Delta H_{AD}} \quad (7)$$

where the overline quantities indicate a fixed value. The Wheatstone bridge (Figure 1) has 7 independent variables $\{\mathbf{Q}, \Theta\}$, so with the 6 Kirchhoff constraints (3)-(4) plus 1 more constraint from (5)-(7) – expressed in numerical form – the problem is fully determined. If the free constraint is specified algebraically but its value is unknown, the problem can be solved probabilistically but its value is underdetermined.

For the following analysis, we choose the incoming flow rate constraint (5) as the free constraint. Applying the MaxEnt method, we need to maximise the entropy (1) subject to its constraints (2), (3), (4) and (5). This is a constrained optimisation problem, for which we apply the method of undetermined multipliers [11]. We therefore maximise the Lagrangian function composed of the entropy function and the sum of residuals (left hand side minus right hand side) of each constraint, each multiplied by an (as yet unknown) Lagrangian multiplier:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\left\langle \ln \frac{p}{q} \right\rangle - \kappa(\langle 1 \rangle - 1) - \mu(\langle \Theta_A \rangle - \overline{\Theta_A}) - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{g}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$ is the dot product of vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , and $\{\kappa, \mu, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}\}$ is the set of Lagrangian multipliers with $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4]^\top$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\beta_1, \beta_2]^\top$. To extremise (8), we take the variation $\delta \mathcal{L} = 0$, whence $\partial \mathcal{L} / \partial p = 0$ for all p [11].

In standard applications of MaxEnt, all expressions in (8) are linear in the expected values, giving the well-known Boltzmann equation of exponential form. For the flow network defined in Figure 1, however, the resistance functions can be nonlinear. Differentiation then gives terms of the form:

$$\frac{\partial R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)}{\partial \langle Q_i \rangle} \frac{\partial \langle Q_i \rangle}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)}{\partial \langle Q_i \rangle} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \int_{\Omega} \cdots \int Q_i p d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta = R'_i(\langle Q_i \rangle) \int_{\Omega} \cdots \int Q_i d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta \quad (9)$$

Extremising (8), moving inside the integrals and rearranging gives the MaxEnt solution (denoted *):

$$p^* = \frac{q}{Z} \exp[-\mu \Theta_A - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{f} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{G}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle)] \quad (10)$$

where $Z = \exp(\kappa + 1)$ is known as the partition function, and

$$\mathbf{G}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle) = \begin{bmatrix} R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)Q_1 + R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)Q_5 - R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)Q_3 \\ R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)Q_2 - R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)Q_4 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)Q_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The partition function has an important meaning in thermodynamics, connected to the free energy concept and the variance of the constraints [11, 12]; here it allows normalisation of the inferred probability (10). Eq. (10) can be solved in conjunction with the 8 constraints (2), (3), (4) and (5), to give 9 equations in the 9 unknowns $\{p^*, Z, \mu, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}\}$. Once (10) is solved, any other expected values not included as constraints – for example (6) or (7) – can be calculated from p^* .

To solve (10), it is necessary to specify the prior. A reasonable choice is a Gaussian multivariate prior composed of the product of independent zero-mean Gaussian distributions:

$$q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta) = \prod_{Q_i \in \mathcal{Q}, \Theta} N(0, \sigma_i) = \prod_{Q_i \in \mathcal{Q}, \Theta} \frac{1}{\sigma_i \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{Q_i^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right) \quad (12)$$

where σ_i is the standard deviation for flow i . For simplicity we can assign $\sigma_i = 1$ for all i . Philosophically, (12) specifies that the problem contains independent and identically distributed (iid) flow rates with no bias for positive or negative values, hence the preference for flow rates near zero rather than approaching $\pm\infty$. However, unlike the truncated uniform distribution, it provides support over $\Omega = \mathbb{R}^7$, avoiding the problems caused by truncation.

In previous studies [3, 4], a double iterative method was developed for numerical solution of the integrals, using a multidimensional quadrature rule with sparse grids. It can however be shown that the expected values (5)-(7) based on (10) with (12) are analytic, even for nonlinear resistance functions.

We now consider the effect of linear or nonlinear resistance functions, in turn:

2.1.1 Linear Resistance Functions

For linear resistance functions (Ohm's law) $R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle) = R_i \langle Q_i \rangle$, with known resistances R_i for each conduit i , the pdf (10) contains the simplified term (11):

$$\mathbf{G}_{lin} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1 Q_1 + R_5 Q_5 - R_3 Q_3 \\ R_2 Q_2 - R_4 Q_4 - R_5 Q_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Substitution of (10) into the normalisation constraint (2) and integration gives the partition function:

$$\begin{aligned} Z = \exp & \left(\frac{3}{2} \alpha_1^2 + \frac{3}{2} \alpha_2^2 + \frac{3}{2} \alpha_3^2 + \frac{3}{2} \alpha_4^2 - \alpha_1 \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \alpha_3 - \alpha_2 \alpha_3 - \alpha_2 \alpha_4 - \alpha_3 \alpha_4 + \frac{1}{2} \mu^2 - \mu \alpha_4 \right. \\ & + R_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 - R_5 \alpha_2 \beta_1 + R_5 \alpha_2 \beta_2 + R_5 \alpha_3 \beta_1 - R_5 \alpha_3 \beta_2 + R_4 \alpha_3 \beta_2 - R_4 \alpha_4 \beta_2 - R_2 \alpha_2 \beta_2 \\ & + R_3 \alpha_1 \beta_1 - R_3 \alpha_3 \beta_1 + R_2 \alpha_4 \beta_2 - R_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1 - R_5^2 \beta_1 \beta_2 + \frac{1}{2} R_3^2 \beta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} R_1^2 \beta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} R_5^2 \beta_2^2 \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{2} R_5^2 \beta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} R_2^2 \beta_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} R_4^2 \beta_2^2 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The remaining 7 constraints (3), (4) and (5) integrate neatly into products containing Z , which cancel to give:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} -\alpha_1 = \overline{\Theta}_A \\ R_1 \beta_1 - R_3 \beta_1 - 3\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 0 \\ -R_1 \beta_1 + R_2 \beta_2 + R_5 \beta_1 - R_5 \beta_2 + \alpha_1 - 3\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\ R_3 \beta_1 - R_4 \beta_2 - R_5 \beta_1 + R_5 \beta_2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 3\alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\ -R_2 \beta_2 + R_4 \beta_2 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 - 3\alpha_4 + \mu = 0 \\ -R_1^2 \beta_1 - R_3^2 \beta_1 - R_5^2 \beta_1 + \beta_2 R_5^2 + R_1 \alpha_1 - R_1 \alpha_2 - R_3 \alpha_1 + \alpha_3 R_3 + R_5 \alpha_2 - R_5 \alpha_3 = 0 \\ -R_2^2 \beta_2 - R_4^2 \beta_2 + R_5^2 \beta_1 - \beta_2 R_5^2 + R_2 \alpha_2 - R_2 \alpha_4 - \alpha_3 R_4 + R_4 \alpha_4 - R_5 \alpha_2 + R_5 \alpha_3 = 0 \end{array} \right] \quad (15)$$

For known resistances, this can be solved for the multipliers $\{\mu, \alpha, \beta\}$, thereby giving Z (14) and p^* (10). For example, specifying $R_1 = R_4 = R_5 = 1$ and $R_2 = R_3 = \frac{1}{2}$ gives

$$\mu = -\frac{149}{49} \overline{\Theta}_A, \quad \alpha = -\left[1, \frac{74}{49}, \frac{75}{49}, \frac{100}{49}\right]^\top \overline{\Theta}_A, \quad \beta = \left[\frac{4}{49}, -\frac{4}{49}\right]^\top \overline{\Theta}_A \quad (16)$$

whence $Z = \exp\left(\frac{149}{98} \overline{\Theta}_A^{-2}\right)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} p^* = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{16 \pi^{7/2}} \exp & \left(-\frac{149 \overline{\Theta}_A^{-2}}{98} + \frac{(3Q_1 + 4Q_2 + 4Q_3 + 3Q_4 - Q_5 + 7\Theta_A + 7\Theta_D) \overline{\Theta}_A}{7} \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{Q_1^2}{2} - \frac{Q_2^2}{2} - \frac{Q_3^2}{2} - \frac{Q_4^2}{2} - \frac{Q_5^2}{2} - \frac{\Theta_A^2}{2} - \frac{\Theta_D^2}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Substitution into (6)-(7) gives the moments:

$$\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle = \left[\frac{3}{7}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{3}{7}, -\frac{1}{7} \right]^\top \overline{\Theta}_A, \quad \langle \Theta \rangle = [1, 1]^\top \overline{\Theta}_A, \quad \langle \Delta H_{AD} \rangle = -\frac{5}{7} \overline{\Theta}_A, \quad (18)$$

Note that the multipliers and moments are algebraic functions of the unknown value $\overline{\Theta}_A$ (all calculations were conducted using Maple 2024 on a MacBook Pro with 8-core Intel i9 processor).

Finally, assigning a numerical value to the free constraint, for example $\overline{\Theta}_A = 2$, yields:

$$\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle = \left[\frac{6}{7}, \frac{8}{7}, \frac{8}{7}, \frac{6}{7}, -\frac{2}{7} \right]^\top, \quad \langle \Theta \rangle = [2, 2]^\top, \quad \langle \Delta H_{AD} \rangle = -\frac{10}{7} \quad (19)$$

These values are identical to those obtained by deterministic solution of the strict forms of the Kirchhoff node and loop constraints (3)-(4).

2.1.2 Nonlinear Resistance Functions

For general nonlinear resistance functions of the form $R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)$, we must retain the term (11). To solve p^* , it is possible to handle the terms $\langle Q_i \rangle$ as if they are constants, subject to the 5 additional moment constraints (6).

Substituting p^* into (2) and integrating gives the partition function:

$$\begin{aligned}
Z = \exp & \left(\frac{3}{2}\alpha_1^2 + \frac{3}{2}\alpha_2^2 + \frac{3}{2}\alpha_3^2 + \frac{3}{2}\alpha_4^2 - \alpha_1\alpha_2 - \alpha_1\alpha_3 - \alpha_2\alpha_3 - \alpha_2\alpha_4 - \alpha_3\alpha_4 + \frac{1}{2}\mu^2 - \mu\alpha_4 \right. \\
& + \frac{1}{2}R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)^2\beta_2^2 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)^2\beta_1\beta_2 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\alpha_2\beta_1 + R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\alpha_2\beta_2 + R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\alpha_3\beta_1 \\
& - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\alpha_3\beta_2 + \frac{1}{2}R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)^2\beta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)^2\beta_2^2 + \frac{1}{2}R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)^2\beta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)^2\beta_2^2 \\
& + \frac{1}{2}R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)^2\beta_1^2 - R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)\alpha_2\beta_2 + R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)\alpha_4\beta_2 + R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)\beta_1\alpha_2 - R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)\alpha_3\beta_1 \\
& \left. + R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)\alpha_3\beta_2 - R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)\alpha_4\beta_2 - R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)\beta_1\alpha_1 + R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)\beta_1\alpha_1 \right) \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

The remaining 12 constraints (3)-(6) again integrate neatly into products containing Z , which cancel to give the nonlinear expressions:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} -\alpha_1 = \overline{\Theta}_A \\ -R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)\beta_1 + R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)\beta_1 - 3\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 0 \\ R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_1 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_2 + R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)\beta_2 - R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)\beta_1 + \alpha_1 - 3\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\ R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)\beta_1 - R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)\beta_2 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_1 + R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 3\alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\ R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)\beta_2 - R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)\beta_2 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 - 3\alpha_4 + \mu = 0 \\ R_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle) + R_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle) - R_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle) = 0 \\ R_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle) - R_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle) - R_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle) = 0 \\ \langle Q_1 \rangle = -R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)\beta_1 + \alpha_1 - \alpha_2 \\ \langle Q_2 \rangle = -R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)\beta_2 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_4 \\ \langle Q_3 \rangle = R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)\beta_1 + \alpha_1 - \alpha_3 \\ \langle Q_4 \rangle = -\alpha_4 + \alpha_3 + R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)\beta_2 \\ \langle Q_5 \rangle = R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_2 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)\beta_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 \end{array} \right] \quad (21)$$

For known functions $R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle)$, this can be solved for the set $\{\mu, \alpha, \beta, \langle Q \rangle\}$, thence for Z and the MaxEnt distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
p^* = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{16\pi^{7/2} Z} \exp & \left(-\frac{Q_1^2}{2} - \frac{Q_2^2}{2} - \frac{Q_3^2}{2} - \frac{Q_4^2}{2} - \frac{Q_5^2}{2} - \frac{\Theta_a^2}{2} - \frac{\Theta_d^2}{2} - R'_1(\langle Q_1 \rangle)Q_1\beta_1 \right. \\
& - R'_2(\langle Q_2 \rangle)Q_2\beta_2 + R'_3(\langle Q_3 \rangle)Q_3\beta_1 + R'_4(\langle Q_4 \rangle)Q_4\beta_2 - R'_5(\langle Q_5 \rangle)Q_5(\beta_1 - \beta_2) \\
& + (-Q_3 + Q_4 - Q_5)\alpha_3 + (\Theta_d - Q_2 - Q_4)\alpha_4 + (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)Q_1 + \alpha_2Q_2 + \alpha_2Q_5 \\
& \left. + (-\Theta_a + Q_3)\alpha_1 - \mu\Theta_d \right) \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

Additional expected values can then be calculated from (22).

As an example, consider the quadratic resistance functions $R_i(\langle Q_i \rangle) = K_i\langle Q_i \rangle|\langle Q_i \rangle|$, where K_i are known parameters and $|\cdot|$ represents an absolute value. This is sometimes used for pipe flows [15]. The derivatives (11) contain terms $R'_i(\langle Q_i \rangle) = 2K_iQ_i|\langle Q_i \rangle|$. Solution of (20), (21) and (22) then gives the multipliers and moments as functions of $\langle Q_i \rangle$ and $\overline{\Theta}_A$, with the possibility of multiple solutions. A trivial solution with vanishing multipliers and moments is also obtained. Constructing a unique solution, assigning the numerical values $K_1 = K_4 = K_5 = 1$, $K_2 = K_3 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\overline{\Theta}_A = 2$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu = -6.08163, \quad \alpha = [-2, -3.10204, -2.97959, -4.08163]^\top, \quad \beta = [0.142857, -0.142857]^\top, \\
Z = 437.74, \quad \langle Q \rangle = [0.85714, 1.14286, 1.14286, 0.85714, -0.28571]^\top \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

Solution of (5) and (7) then gives $\langle \Theta_A \rangle = \langle \Theta_D \rangle = 2$ and $\langle \Delta H_{AD} \rangle = -1.38776$. The expected values are again identical to those obtained by deterministic solution of the strict forms of the Kirchhoff node and loop constraints (3)-(4).

For either type of resistance function, the MaxEnt problem can be reformulated using the free constraint on an internal flow rate (6) or the head difference (7) instead of the incoming flow rate (5). The resulting formulations have similar characteristics to those outlined above.

2.2 Prediction of Flow Rates, Potentials and Resistances

2.2.1 One Unknown Resistance

We now modify the problem specification to consider unknown flow rates with one unknown resistance R_4 , expanding on the original purpose of the Wheatstone bridge [10]. For simplicity we adopt linear resistance functions.

By symmetry, it is tempting to define the pdf as $p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R)$. This approach, however, requires the solution of a large multidimensional integral, which although analytic is very slow (> 1 hour in Maple 2024 on a MacBook Pro). If R_4 is the only unknown resistance, it is preferable to adopt the pdf $p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)$, giving the relative entropy:

$$\mathfrak{H}_{\Omega \times \mathcal{P}} = - \int_{\Omega \times \mathcal{P}} \dots \int p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)} d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta dR_4 = - \left\langle \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)} \right\rangle \quad (24)$$

where $\mathcal{P} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is the domain of R_4 . Eq. (24) is subject to constraints on normalisation (2), Kirchhoff's node and loop laws (3)-(4), and possibly also on the expected values of external flow rate(s) (5), internal flow rate(s) (6) and/or head difference(s) (7). Two such expected value constraints render the problem fully determined.

It is tempting to pose this problem using the same formulation as for linear resistances (§2.1.1), using the term $R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle$ for the head difference along the 4th pipe, which appears in the second head loop constraint (4) and also (in one of two alternatives) in the head difference constraint (7). It is instructive to do so, since it provides a deterministic solution that is incorrect. This solution also contains quadratic roots, with the possibility of multiple solutions. This reveals an important feature of MaxEnt analysis: the problem specification must match the problem precisely. In this case, since R_4 is unknown, the constraints must be written in terms of its moment $\langle R_4 \rangle$, even though this is unknown. The head difference along the 4th conduit is therefore $\langle R_4 \rangle \langle Q_4 \rangle$. Despite using linear resistance functions, the problem has become nonlinear!

We next choose a prior over the flow rates and R_4 . Since the resistances can never be negative, it is reasonable to consider a non-Gaussian prior, for example the lognormal, gamma, inverse gamma or Gumbel distributions [14]. Each of these is defined for $\mathcal{P} = [0, \infty]$, has a peak at small positive R_4 and vanishes for $R_4 \rightarrow \infty$. However, each such function creates a problem in the definition of expected values. For example, using the lognormal distribution based on $r_4 = \ln R_4$, we find that $\langle R_4 \rangle = \langle e^{\ln R_4} \rangle \neq e^{\langle \ln R_4 \rangle}$, so moments defined in linear space cannot in general be connected to those defined in log space. In consequence, the constraints on the resistances will have a different mathematical meaning. For this reason, we here choose a Gaussian prior for R_4 despite its philosophical deficiencies, which is analytically tractable and does give correct deterministic solutions. This gives the joint prior:

$$\begin{aligned} q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4) &= \left[\prod_{Q_i \in \mathbf{Q}, \Theta} N(Q_i | 0, \sigma_i) \right] N(r_4 | m_4, \varsigma_4) \\ &= \left[\prod_{Q_i \in \mathbf{Q}, \Theta} \frac{1}{\sigma_i \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{Q_i^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right) \right] \frac{1}{\varsigma_4 \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(R_4 - m_4)^2}{2\varsigma_4^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where m_4 and ς_4 are the prior mean and standard deviation for R_4 . For simplicity we choose $m_4 = 0$ and $\varsigma_4 = 1$.

The constraints (2), (3) and (5) are the same as those previously, now expressed in terms of $p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, R_4)$. The others must be transformed carefully. Kirchhoff's loop laws (4) are now:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1 \langle Q_1 \rangle + R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle - R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle \\ R_2 \langle Q_2 \rangle - \langle R_4 \rangle \langle Q_4 \rangle - R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \hat{\mathbf{g}}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle R_4 \rangle) \quad (26)$$

while the head difference constraint (7) is:

$$0 = R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle + \langle R_4 \rangle \langle Q_4 \rangle + \overline{\Delta H_{AD}} = \hat{h}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle R_4 \rangle) \quad (27)$$

(this can also be written in terms of R_1 and R_2 , as per (7)). The Lagrangian becomes:

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}} = - \left\langle \ln \frac{p}{q} \right\rangle - \kappa (\langle 1 \rangle - 1) - \mu (\langle \Theta_A \rangle - \overline{\Theta_A}) - \eta \hat{h} - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{g}} \quad (28)$$

where η is the head difference multiplier. To solve $\hat{\mathcal{L}} = 0$, the moments inside $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ and \hat{h} must be differentiated carefully. Moving inside the integrals, the MaxEnt solution is:

$$p^* = \frac{q}{Z} \exp[-\mu \Theta_A - \eta \hat{H} - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{f} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{G}}] \quad (29)$$

with

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1 Q_1 - R_3 Q_3 + R_5 Q_5 \\ R_2 Q_2 - \langle R_4 \rangle Q_4 - R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle - R_5 Q_5 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{H} = [R_3 Q_3 + \langle R_4 \rangle Q_4 + R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle] \quad (30)$$

Note that the derivatives now contain two terms $\langle R_4 \rangle Q_4$ and $R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle$, an essential feature of this problem. Substitution of (38)-(39) with (25) into (2) and integration gives the partition function:

$$\begin{aligned}
Z = \exp & \left(\frac{(\beta_2 - \eta)^2 \langle R_4 \rangle^2}{2} + (\alpha_3 - \alpha_4)(\beta_2 - \eta) \langle R_4 \rangle + \frac{(\beta_2 - \eta)^2 \langle Q_4 \rangle^2}{2} + \frac{\beta_1^2 R_1^2}{2} - \beta_1(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) R_1 \right. \\
& + \frac{\beta_2^2 R_2^2}{2} - \beta_2(\alpha_2 - \alpha_4) R_2 + \frac{(\beta_1 - \eta)^2 R_3^2}{2} + (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3)(\beta_1 - \eta) R_3 + \frac{(\beta_1 - \beta_2)^2 R_5^2}{2} + (\alpha_2 - \alpha_3)(\beta_2 - \beta_1) R_5 \\
& \left. - \alpha_1 \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \alpha_3 - \alpha_2 \alpha_3 - \alpha_2 \alpha_4 - \alpha_3 \alpha_4 + \frac{3\alpha_1^2}{2} + \frac{3\alpha_2^2}{2} + \frac{3\alpha_3^2}{2} + \frac{3\alpha_4^2}{2} + \frac{\mu^2}{2} + \mu \alpha_1 \right) \quad (31)
\end{aligned}$$

The constraints (3), (5), (26) and (27), as well as all other moments, again integrate neatly with cancellation of Z . The set of constraints augmented with $\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle$ and $\langle R_4 \rangle$ become:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c}
-\mu - \alpha_1 = \overline{\Theta_A} \\
R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle + \langle Q_4 \rangle \langle R_4 \rangle = -\overline{\Delta H_{AD}} \\
R_1 \beta_1 - R_3 \beta_1 + R_3 \eta - 3\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 - \mu = 0 \\
-R_1 \beta_1 + R_2 \beta_2 + R_5 \beta_1 - R_5 \beta_2 + \alpha_1 - 3\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\
R_3 \beta_1 - R_3 \eta - R_5 \beta_1 + R_5 \beta_2 - \beta_2 \langle R_4 \rangle + \eta \langle R_4 \rangle + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 3\alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\
-R_2 \beta_2 + \beta_2 \langle R_4 \rangle - \eta \langle R_4 \rangle + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 - 3\alpha_4 = 0 \\
R_1 \langle Q_1 \rangle - R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle + R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle = 0 \\
R_2 \langle Q_2 \rangle - R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle - \langle Q_4 \rangle \langle R_4 \rangle = 0 \\
\langle Q_1 \rangle = -R_1 \beta_1 + \alpha_1 - \alpha_2 \\
\langle Q_2 \rangle = -R_2 \beta_2 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_4 \\
\langle Q_3 \rangle = R_3 \beta_1 - R_3 \eta + \alpha_1 - \alpha_3 \\
\langle Q_4 \rangle = \beta_2 \langle R_4 \rangle - \eta \langle R_4 \rangle + \alpha_3 - \alpha_4 \\
\langle Q_5 \rangle = -R_5 \beta_1 + R_5 \beta_2 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 \\
\langle R_4 \rangle = \beta_2 \langle Q_4 \rangle - \eta \langle Q_4 \rangle
\end{array} \right] \quad (32)$$

This set of 14 equations in 14 unknowns $\{\mu, \eta, \alpha, \beta, \langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle R_4 \rangle\}$ can be solved in terms of $\overline{\Theta_A}$ and $\overline{\Delta H_{AD}}$, thereby giving Z and the MaxEnt distribution p^* .

For numerical solution, setting $R_1 = R_5 = 1$, $R_2 = R_3 = \frac{1}{2}$, $\overline{\Theta_A} = 2$ and $\overline{\Delta H_{AD}} = -\frac{10}{7}$ gives an extension of the fully determined problem with linear resistances analysed in §2.1.1. Solution gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu &= -3.86508, \quad \eta = -3.10317, \quad \alpha = [1.86508, 2.17460, 1.69048, 2.0]^\top, \\
\beta &= [-1.166667, -1.93651]^\top, \quad Z = 721.7, \\
\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle &= [0.85714, 1.14286, 1.14286, 0.85714, -0.28571]^\top, \quad \langle R_4 \rangle = 1.00000
\end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

The expected values are the same as those calculated previously, with $\langle R_4 \rangle$ in place of R_4 .

2.2.2 Resistances with Uncertainty

An attendee at the MaxEnt 2025 conference asked an interesting question: what if the resistances R_1, R_2, R_3 and R_5 are also uncertain, being constrained only the mean? Using the same settings as §2.2.1 wherever possible, this problem can also be solved within the MaxEnt framework. The pdf is now $p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R})$, giving the relative entropy and prior:

$$\mathfrak{H}_{\Omega \times \mathcal{P}'} = - \int \cdots \int_{\Omega \times \mathcal{P}'} p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R}) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R})}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R})} d\mathbf{Q} d\Theta d\mathbf{R} = - \left\langle \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R})}{q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R})} \right\rangle \quad (34)$$

$$q(\mathbf{Q}, \Theta, \mathbf{R}) = \left[\prod_{Q_i \in \mathbf{Q}, \Theta} \frac{1}{\sigma_i \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left(-\frac{Q_i^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right) \right] \left[\prod_{R_j \in \mathbf{R}} \frac{1}{\varsigma_j \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left(-\frac{(R_j - m_j)^2}{2\varsigma_j^2} \right) \right] \quad (35)$$

where $\mathcal{P}' \subseteq \mathbb{R}^5$ is the resistance domain, while m_j and ς_j are the prior mean and standard deviation for R_j . We again choose $\sigma_i = 1$, $m_j = 0$ and $\varsigma_j = 1$ for all i and j . The Kirchhoff constraints are now:

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \langle R_1 \rangle \langle Q_1 \rangle + \langle R_5 \rangle \langle Q_5 \rangle - \langle R_3 \rangle \langle Q_3 \rangle \\ \langle R_2 \rangle \langle Q_2 \rangle - \langle R_4 \rangle \langle Q_4 \rangle - \langle R_5 \rangle \langle Q_5 \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \check{g}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{R} \rangle) \\
0 &= \langle R_3 \rangle \langle Q_3 \rangle + \langle R_4 \rangle \langle Q_4 \rangle + \overline{\Delta H_{AD}} = \check{h}(\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{R} \rangle)
\end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The Lagrangian is:

$$\check{\mathcal{L}} = -\left\langle \ln \frac{p}{q} \right\rangle - \kappa(\langle 1 \rangle - 1) - \mu(\langle \Theta_A \rangle - \overline{\Theta_A}) - \eta \check{h} - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \check{\mathbf{g}} - \boldsymbol{\rho} \cdot \langle \check{\mathbf{R}} \rangle \quad (37)$$

where $\check{\mathbf{R}} = [R_1, R_2, R_3, R_5]^\top$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho} = [\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_5]^\top$ is the corresponding multiplier. The MaxEnt solution is:

$$p^* = \frac{q}{Z} \exp[-\mu\Theta_A - \eta\check{H} - \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{f} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \check{\mathbf{G}} - \boldsymbol{\rho} \cdot \check{\mathbf{R}}] \quad (38)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\mathbf{G}} &= \left[\begin{array}{l} \langle R_1 \rangle Q_1 + R_1 \langle Q_1 \rangle - \langle R_3 \rangle Q_3 - R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle + \langle R_5 \rangle Q_5 + R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle \\ \langle R_2 \rangle Q_2 + R_2 \langle Q_2 \rangle - \langle R_4 \rangle Q_4 - R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle - \langle R_5 \rangle Q_5 - R_5 \langle Q_5 \rangle \end{array} \right], \\ \check{H} &= [\langle R_3 \rangle Q_3 + R_3 \langle Q_3 \rangle + \langle R_4 \rangle Q_4 + R_4 \langle Q_4 \rangle] \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

For known $\langle \check{\mathbf{R}} \rangle$, this gives a set of 20 equations in 20 unknowns $\{p^*, Z, \mu, \eta, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\rho}, \langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle, \langle R_4 \rangle\}$. The partition function is again analytic, factoring out of the constraints to enable a simplified solution (this is left as an exercise for capable readers).

Checking the numerical solution, setting $\langle R_1 \rangle = \langle R_5 \rangle = 1$, $\langle R_2 \rangle = \langle R_3 \rangle = \frac{1}{2}$, $\overline{\Theta_A} = 2$ and $\overline{\Delta H_{AD}} = -\frac{10}{7}$ extends the problems analysed in §2.1.1 and §2.2.1. Solution gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= -3.86508, \quad \eta = -3.10317, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha} = [1.86508, 2.17460, 1.69048, 2.0]^\top, \\ \boldsymbol{\beta} &= [-1.166667, -1.93651]^\top, \quad \boldsymbol{\rho} = [3.48413 \times 10^{-9}, 1.71315, 1.71315, -0.78005]^\top, \quad Z = 2519.039, \\ \langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle &= [0.85714, 1.14286, 1.14286, 0.85714, -0.28571]^\top, \quad \langle R_4 \rangle = 1.00000 \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

The multipliers $\{\mu, \eta, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}\}$ and moments $\langle \mathbf{Q} \rangle$ and $\langle R_4 \rangle$ have the same values as those in §2.2.1.

3. CONCLUSION

In this study, the MaxEnt method is applied to the prediction of (probabilistic) flow rates and potential differences on a Wheatstone bridge [9, 10], to provide a simple example of a potential-driven flow network. Using a multivariate Gaussian prior, the MaxEnt formulation is found to be analytic (using Maple 2025 on a MacBook Pro), even for nonlinear resistance functions. The analytical form of the partition function enables factorisation and rapid solution, without requiring the numerical solution of integrals reported in previous studies [3, 4]. Several problem specifications are analysed both algebraically and numerically, including for (a) linear resistance functions, (b) non-linear (quadratic) resistance functions, (c) an unknown resistance and (d) uncertain resistances, to demonstrate various nonlinear formulations of the MaxEnt method. The framework developed here can be applied to larger potential-driven flow networks such as water distribution or electrical networks, containing linear or nonlinear resistance functions [3, 4, 5].

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